

Radio Science

Supporting Data Set - 2

for the paper entitled

Observation and Analysis of Anomalous Terrestrial Diffraction as a Mechanism of Electromagnetic Precursors of Earthquakes

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Contents of this file

Radio Wave Data Observed in Iwata, Shizuoka Prefecture / Sakai, Osaka Prefecture

Introduction

This file contains the long-term observation data of the radio wave power received at the Iwata and Sakai observation stations in Figure 1, which provide perspectives on the normal and abnormal states of the radio wave signals and the occurrence of the earthquakes.

The data also provide a reference as to whether they are influenced by other natural environmental phenomena such as meteorological and ionospheric effects, and any radio interference from the solar activity suggested by the geomagnetic data.

The earthquake, meteorological and geomagnetic data are from the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) website. The ionospheric data are from the website of the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology (NICT), Japan. The list of earthquakes was obtained by searching the internet database of JMA using the conditions of area, magnitude and seismic intensity shown below along with Figure 2.

Period of the Radiowave Data Observed in Shizuoka / Sakai:

Iwata City, Shizuoka, Japan, Mar. 2021 – Mar. 2023,

Sakai City, Osaka, Japan, Mar. 2021 – Mar. 2023

Japan Meteorological Agency Earthquake Database Search Options:

EQ Search Area: Kanagawa, Shizuoka, Aichi, Mie, Nara, Wakayama (Red Regions in Fig. 2)

EQ Conditions: Magnitude > 0, and Local Seismic Intensity > = 1

Figure 1 Locations of radio broadcast stations (●) and observation stations (■).

Figure 2 Region to search for earthquakes in this file: 6 prefectures near Iwata.

Observation Stations (Figure 1):

Iwata City, Shizuoka Pref., horizontal polarization
(E137° 49'20", N34° 39'20", antenna altitude 4 m above sea level)

Sakai City, Osaka Pref., vertical polarization
(E135° 28'30", N34° 34'01", antenna altitude 17 m above sea level)

Radio Broadcast Stations (Figure 1):

78.9 MHz, 3 kW, Tsu, horizontal polarization (E136° 26'01", N34° 43'57", altitude 320 m)

79.2MHz, 1 kW, Shizuoka, horizontal polarization (E138° 27'56", N34° 58'27", altitude 300 m)

80.9 MHz, no radio broadcast in Japan, referenced to monitor broadband interference.

82.5 MHz, 10 kW, Nagoya, horizontal polarization (E136° 58'04", N35° 08'49", altitude 227 m)

84.7 MHz, 5 kW, Yokohama, horizontal polarization (E139° 13'51", N35° 26'29", altitude 1240 m)

88.8 MHz, 1 kW, Shizuoka, horizontal polarization (E138° 27'56", N34° 58'27", altitude 300 m)

82.7 MHz, 10 W, Aritagawa, horizontal polarization (E135° 22'39", N34° 05'04", altitude 590 m)

83.2 MHz, 30W, Hashimoto, horizontal polarization (E135° 32'33", N34° 17'29", altitude 296 m)

83.4 MHz, 10 W, Shimokitayama, horizontal polarization (E135° 57'46", N33° 59'06", altitude 798 m)

Example of the Observed Data in S-1 Format (Period: Mar. 8, 2021 – Mar. 7, 2023)

[Descriptions]

JMA EQ Database information searched in the specified region with the conditions above. Local seismic intensity and magnitude are shown in ().

JMA Magnitude

Local Seismic Intensity Index in Japan

Radiowave in West Japan Area

Radiowave in West Japan Area

Radiowave in West Japan Area

Radiowave from Shizuoka to Iwata

Radiowave from Yokohama to Iwata

Radiowave from Nagoya to Iwata

Frequency of No-Radiobroadcast (Measured for Detecting Noises)

Radiowave from Shizuoka to Iwata

Radiowave from Tsu to Iwata

Atmospheric Temperature (right) and Precipitation (left) in Shizuoka (JMA)

Ionogram of E-Layer in Kokubunji in Tokyo (NICT)

Ionogram of E-Layer in Wakkanai in Hokkaido (NICT)

Geomagnetic Field (Total Intensity) in Kakioka (JMA)

Year, Month, Date, Hour, Min in JST. Plot span is all 10 days.

Another Example of the Observed Data in S-1 Format (Same Format as Above)

[Descriptions]

JMA EQ Database information searched in the specified region with the conditions above. Local seismic intensity and magnitude are shown in ().

JMA Magnitude

Local Seismic Intensity Index in Japan

Radiowave in West Japan Area

Radiowave in West Japan Area

Radiowave in West Japan Area

Radiowave from Shizuoka to Iwata

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Geomagnetic Field (Total Intensity) in Kakioka (JMA)

Year, Month, Date, Hour, Min in JST. Plot span is all 10 days.

Radio Wave Data

Observed in Iwata, Shizuoka Prefecture / Sakai, Osaka Prefecture

Mar. 8, 2021 – Mar. 7, 2023

